

Status of Women in Haryana: A District Level Analysis

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Abstract: The status of women is studied from various perspectives. The status of women is defined as ‘the extent of control that a person has over her life, derived from the access to social, economic, health resources and political power and autonomy enjoyed in the process of decision making’. The status of women is also the emulative result of past and present position of women in the society which indicates whether they have been subject to discriminate or not. As women status is a vast field with a multitude of indicators, mainly indicators of the status of women are economic, health, education, governance and crime against women. The present study is an attempt to analysis the disparities in the status of women in Haryana state at two point of time for the year 2007-08 and 2015-16.

Keywords: women status, economic, health, education, governance, Haryana.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is unfortunate that because of centuries of indolence, ignorance and conservatism, the actual and potential role of women in the society has been ignored, preventing them from making their rightful contribution to social progress. It is also because of distorted or partial information about their contribution to family and society that they are denied from their rightful status and access to developmental resources and services contributing to their marginalization. Though, there have been cases of women predominance in different ages and in different societies, it has been evidenced that no society in the world has provided equally women status with men. Women have exploited and restricted by deprived of educational opportunities, avenues for gainful employment, social customs, religious practice and economically dependency. Women and men have been performing different roles. It is also believed that a woman is not treated as man. This gender discrimination also prevails in the development process, where gender bias takes the form of alienation of women from the mainstream, with lesser or no benefits to their efforts. Male superiority and female inferiority are accepted social norms in India. Gender based discrimination represents the ugly face of society of our times.

The reality of women’s status on the basis of socio-economic condition has put them in the most disadvantageous and deprived communities of the world. The very rigidly defined roles and activities of women, widespread illiteracy among the women and *pardah* system have contributed to the social degradation of women in India. In India gender relations are influenced by traditional hierarchies based on patriarchy, caste and ethnicity and compounded by inequalities of wealth and power. The position of women seems to have deteriorated, especially in the north India, due to their limited access of education, health and employment. In the present paper, disparities in the status of women in Haryana have been studied on the basis of mainly five important indicators.

In every field women are confronted with many challenges and suffer from many disadvantages as compared to men in the area of education, work participation, health, economic condition and violence against women [1]. The status of women through their decision making power for the household activities in two villages namely Aurepalle and Dokur of Mahbubnagar district of Telangana state in India. It is concluded that men have a very less power in the household decisions then women. Mostly household decision has been taken by women where small issues and small expensive

amounts, has followed by joint decisions and the role of men is high where expensive amounts is huge to be invest [2]. The mostly women in Madurai district of Tamil Nadu has been able to take decision independently related to family budget, education of their children, family's health and medicine and personal needs etc. [3]. Women empowerment of rural areas through entrepreneurial activities of SHGs followed by economic empowerment, social, entrepreneurial and technological empowerment [4]. Economic development can be reduced inequality between men and women in particular education, earning opportunities, rights and health [5]. The rural women have interested towards the entrepreneurial activities in rural India [6]. The women empowerment through decision making power among rural women at household level in three Divisional Secretariat Divisions namely, Chankanai, Kopay, Sandilipay of Sri Lanka. The results of the study reported that women have decision making power in cooking, visits to relative's house and health care but have not decision power on income, expenditure and children's education during the study period 2006-07 [7]. The Raichow village of Comilla Sadar upazila (Bangladesh) has been selected for the study during 2009. The author's found that participation of women in joint decision is comparatively higher in mainly six areas out of thirteen like, house making, education of children and family planning etc [8]. The decision making empowerment of women members of the Self Help Groups of Madurai District of Indian state namely Tamil Nadu. The author is found that there is significant relationship between Education, caste, marital status, experience and the decision making empowerment of women but age, occupation and nature of family have no significant relation with decision making empowerment of women in SHGs [9]. The maximum involvement of women in agriculture sector in the Centre region of India and follow by West, North regions etc. and highest participation of women in manufacturing sector by the East region follow by South and North region etc. [10]. The decision making power of women was lower for Muslim and SC and both variables are negative and significant but Economic factors are positive and significant with female autonomy [11]. The status of women by comparing two time period i.e.2001 and 2011 in Haryana. The author's found that during 2001, Fridabad, Gurugram and Kaithal districts are the most endanger districts and by 2011, Mahendragarh, Hisar, Jhajjar and Rohtak districts are showed poor women status, while Panchkula, Sirsa and Kurukshetra districts are the better performing districts in the state [12].

B. Objective of the Study:

The main objective of the study is:

O₁: To analyze the inter-district disparities in the status of women in Haryana state.

C. Hypothesis:

The major hypotheses of the study are:

H₀: There is no significance difference in the status of women among the districts in Haryana state.

H₁: There is significance difference in the status of women among the districts in Haryana state.

II. METHOD

A. Scope of the Study:

The present study aims to study the status of women in Haryana by taking a number of socio-economic indicators. It also aims to analyze the inter-district situation in women's status by comparing two time period i.e, 2007-08 and 2015-16 for few indicators. It attempts to find out the spatial districts where status of women has improved or deteriorated.

B. Data Collection

As women's status is a vast field with a multitude of indicators, we focus on its seafront indicators. Specifically, we analyze five indicators of women's status: economic, Governance, Health, crime and Education. Every indicator has many sub-variables. The secondary source of data is used to analyze. All indicators which is discusses above have been collected mainly from Census of India, DLHS-3 Survey, NFHS-4, NCRB and Haryana Statistical Abstract (Various Issues).

C. Research Methodology

The status of women is multi-dimensional process and it cannot be fully evaluated by a single indicator. So, it is necessary to construct a composite index. There are various methods (e.g., principal component analysis, aggregation method,

ranking method, multiple factor analysis, monetary index and ratio index) for combining the effect of various indicators. But most of these methods are having their own limitations. The Wroclow Taxonomic Method is used to construct the composite index to obtain a statistical method of determining homogenous units or types of things in an n-dimensional vectorial space.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Inter-Districts Disparities in the Status of Women in Haryana State:

In the present section of the chapter an attempt has been made to discuss the inter-districts disparities in the women status in Haryana state. Because of non-existence Palwal district is not included in the study for the year of 2007-08. The composite index of women status has been computed by the help of Wroclow Taxonomic method, ordinal rank has been given to the districts and stages of women status of all districts of Haryana. Various indicators have been used for identification the stages of women status.

Table 1. Districts wise Composite Index (CI) of Overall indicators, rank of districts and stages of women status in Haryana.

Sr. No.	District	(2007-08)			(2015-16)		
		C.I.	Stage	Rank	C.I.	Stage	Rank
01	AMBALA	0.5564	III	08	0.6351	III	10
02	BHIWANI	0.5845	II	12	0.6277	III	09
03	FARIDABAD	0.6502	II	18	0.6892	II	16
04	FATEHABAD	0.5312	III	04	0.6405	II	11
05	GURUGRAM	0.5020	III	02	0.6251	III	08
06	HISAR	0.6159	II	17	0.6456	II	12
07	JHAJJAR	0.7708	I	19	0.5728	III	04
08	JIND	0.6077	II	15	0.6933	II	17
09	KAITHAL	0.6017	II	13	0.6044	III	07
10	KARNAL	0.5382	III	05	0.6844	II	15
11	KURUKSHETRA	0.5723	II	09	0.5734	III	05
12	MAHENDERGARH	0.6068	II	14	0.6809	II	14
13	NUH	0.8583	I	20	0.9080	I	21
14	PALWAL	NA	NA	NA	0.5672	III	03
15	PANCHKULA	0.4473	III	01	0.7499	II	20
16	PANIPAT	0.5835	II	11	0.6538	II	13
17	REWARI	0.5213	III	03	0.5910	III	06
18	ROHTAK	0.6108	II	16	0.7464	II	19
19	SIRSA	0.5388	III	06	0.6970	II	18
20	SONIPAT	0.5760	II	10	0.2477	IV	01
21	YAMUNANAGAR	0.5555	III	07	0.5159	IV	02

Stage= stage of women status, I = low women status, II = middle low women status

III = high middle women status, IV = high women status, NA (Not Available)

It is evident from the table 1 that in overall indices, Panchkula district had ranked first in the women status and Nuh district had ranked last in 2007-08. It is reveal also that the value of composite index of women status in Haryana was varying from 0.4473 to 0.8583. It is indicate that there was the greatest regional disparity in women status of overall indices in Haryana. The highest status of women in overall indices was in these top five districts namely Panchkula, Gurugra, Rewari and Fatehabad and Karnal. The value of composite index of women status in overall indices was varying from 0.4473 to 0.5382 which is show that there was the greatest disparity in women status. All these districts were put in stage of high middle women status (III). Nuh, Jhajjar, Faridabadr, Hisar and Rohtak these top five districts were having lowest women status and the value of composite index of women status was varying from 0.8583 to 0.6108 in these districts. It is indicated that there was the greatest disparity in women status. In these five districts two districts namely Nuh, and Jhajjar were in the category of low women status stage (I) and Faridabad, Hisar and Rohtak districts were put in the stage of middle low women status (II). There is a significant difference in the women status among districts in Haryana state. Therefore, the hypothesis (H_0) is rejected.

Table 1 also presents that in 2015-16, the value of composite index of women status was varying from 0.2477 to 0.9080. It is show here that there was greatest disparity in overall indices of women status in all over Haryana. Sonipat district had the lowest value of composite index of women status that shows the highest women status in overall indices and Nuh district had the highest value of overall indices that shows the lowest women status in overall indices. A total of five districts namely, Sonipat, Yamunanagar, Palwal, Jhajjar and Kurukshetra had the highest women status and the value of composite index was varying from 0.2477 to 0.5734 in these districts. It is indicated that there was the greatest disparity in women status in these districts. The lowest status of women was depicted in these five districts namely, Nuh, Panchkula, Rohtak, Sirsa and Jind. The value of composite index of women status was varying from 0.9080 to 0.6933 that is show that there was the greatest disparity in women status. Nuh district was placed in stage of low women status category (I) and other four districts were placed in stage of middle low women status category (II). There is a significant difference in the women status among districts in Haryana state. Therefore, the hypothesis (H_0) is rejected.

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

A. Conclusions

Analysis reveals that most of the districts have experienced considerable change in women status in Haryana during the period from 2007-08 to 2015-16. After analysis the data the major findings of the study are following.

- Panchkula district has ranked first in overall indicators of women status in 2007-08 and this district has experienced considerable decrease in women status in 2015-16.
- Nuh district had ranked 20 in overall indicators during the year 2007-08 and had ranked 21 in 2015-16. This district was on last rank of the State, It means there was no improvement in the status of women.
- These districts were experienced considerable increase in overall status of women namely, Bhiwani, Faridabad, Hisar, Jhajjar, Kaithal, Kurukshetra, Sonipat and Yamunanagar in 2015-16 than the year 2007-08.
- These districts namely, Fatehabad, Gurugram, Karnal, Panchkula and Sirsa were experienced decrease in overall status of women in 2015-16 as compare 2007-08.
- These districts namely, Ambala, Jind, Mahendergarh, Panipat, Rewari, Nuh and Rohtak were experienced almost stability in overall women status in 2015-16 and 2007-08.
- Any district was not in the stage of high women status in 2007-08 and two districts namely Sonipat and Yamunanagar were in the stage of high women status in 2015-16. Sonipat district had ranked first and Yamunanagar had ranked second in overall indices of women status in 2015-16.
- Total seven districts of the State were in the (III) stage of women status in overall indices in 2007-08 and in 2015-16, total eight districts were in the same stage of women status. It is indicate that there was sharp increasing in women status in 2015-16 than the year 2007-08.
- It is evident from the study that almost 50 per cent districts of the State were in the (II) stage of women status in overall indices in both time period 2007-08 and 2015-16.
- Two districts namely Nuh and Jhajjar were in the stage of low women status (I) in 2007-08 and only one district namely Nuh was in (I) stage of women status in 2015-16. It is indicate that there was sharp declining in district that had low women status.

B. Suggestions

There is an urgent need to improve the status of women in Haryana. Some suggestions have been made in the following:-

1. Government should increase employment for women in Sonipat, Rewari, Panchkula, Nuh, Mahendergarh, Karnal and Jind districts.
2. Government should provide better health services for women in Gurugram, Kaithal, Kurukshetra, Mahendergarh, Nuh, Rewari and Rohtak districts.

3. Government should focus on female education in Hisar, Jhajjar, Jind, Mahendergarh, Nuh, Panchkula, Rohtak and Sirsa districts.
4. Government should increase women participation in local government in the Faridabad, Gurugram, Jind, Nuh, and Panchkula districts.
5. Government should check crimes against women in Faridabad, Gurugram, Hisar, Rohtak and Sonapat districts.
6. Government should focus on those districts where the status of women is very low i.e., Nuh, Panchkula, Rohtak, Sirsa, Jind, Faridabad etc.
7. Considering the value of education in relation of health, it is important to give priority to literacy development programmes among women in Haryana.
8. Girls' enrolment in higher educational institutions should be encouraged through reservation of seats.
9. Construction of Anganwadi in every primary school, provide supplementary nutrition to females and girls will enhance the status of women.
10. Women should be encouraged to take up professional jobs, which can enhance their socio-economic status.
11. Government should implement rules and laws strictly to protect the rights of women.

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